

refill liq N₂
beamline exit slit 150 μm
analyzer 500 μm

17:02

refill liq N₂ 17:10

17:24

17:42

refill liq N₂ 17:51

18:09

Durchgeführt von/Performed by

Datum/Date

Gesehen/witnessed:

Glucose 1M + 50mM NaCl

pH 4.8

Mar-20-0022
C1s

EK = 552 - 564 eV @ 50meV; E_p = 100eV 850eV
4 fps #4

Mar-20-0023
O1s calib

EK = 305 - 320 eV @ 100meV 850eV
#2

Mar-20-0024
O1s

EK = 591 - 603 eV @ 50meV 1135eV
#4

Mar-20-0025
VB

EK = ~~560~~ 560 - 595 eV @ 75meV 600eV
#4

pH 7.6

Mar-20-0026
C1s

EK = 552 - 564 eV @ 50meV; 850eV
#4

Mar-20-0027
O1s calib

EK = 305 - 320 eV @ 100meV 850eV
#2

Mar-20-0028
O1s

EK = 591 - 603 eV @ 50meV 1135eV
#4

Mar-20-0029
VB

EK = 560 - 595 eV @ 75meV 600eV
#4

pH 10

Mar-20-0030
C1s

EK = 552 - 564 eV @ 50meV; 850eV
#4

Mar-20-0031
O1s calib

EK = 305 - 320 eV @ 100meV 850eV
#2

Durchgeführt von/Performed by

Datum/Date

Gesehen/witnessed:

refill lig N₂ traps
18:58

refill lig N₂ 19:25

Mar 20-0032 EK = 591-603 eV @ 50 meV #4 1135 eV
0.1s

Mar 20-0033 EK = 560-585 eV @ 75 meV #4 600 eV
VB

pH: 13

Mar 20-0034 EK = 552-564 eV @ 50 meV #4 850 eV
0.1s

Mar 20-0035 EK = 305-320 eV @ 100 meV #2 850 eV
0.1s calib

Mar 20-0036 EK = 591-603 eV @ 50 meV #4 1135 eV
0.1s

Mar 20-0037 EK = 560-585 eV @ 75 meV #4 600 eV
VB

pH: 2

Mar 20-0038 EK = 552-564 eV @ 50 meV #4 850 eV
0.1s

Mar 20-0039 EK = 305-320 eV @ 100 meV #2 850 eV
0.1s calib

Mar 20-0040 AS Mar 20-0036 1135 eV
0.1s

Mar 20-0041 AS Mar 20-0037 600 eV
VB

Filled cold traps →

Switch to 1M Glucose pH = 10.5 + 50 mM NaCl

Grating slit: 1100 l/mm, 9 nm

exit slit: 150 μ m

analyzer slit: 500 slit

MCP voltage: 1550 V

jet grounded to
chamber → 0V

stainless steel screws
instead of plastic screws

Filled cold traps

This sample is yellowish →
(pH 11.5 and 10.5 are not)
This seems to be pKa

¹⁷
Mar-22-0017 1M Glucose pH = 10.5 850eV
C1s KE = 552 - 564 eV, PE = 100 eV,
50 meV steps, 4 fps #6
p_{main} = 2.2 e-6 mbar

Mar-22-0018 KE = 305 - 320 eV, PE = 100 eV, 850eV
0.1s calib 100 meV steps, 4 fps #2

Switch to 1M Glucose pH = 11.5 + 50 mM NaCl

Mar-22-0019 1M Glucose pH = 11.5 850eV
C1s KE = 552 - 564 eV, PE = 100 eV,
50 meV steps, 4 fps #6
p_{main} = 1.8 e-4 mbar

Mar-22-0020 KE = 305 - 320 eV, PE = 100 eV, 850eV
0.1s calib 100 meV steps, 4 fps #2

Switch to 1M Glucose pH = 12.5 + 50 mM NaCl

Mar-22-0021 1M Glucose pH = 12.5 850eV
C1s KE = 552 - 564 eV, PE = 100 eV,
50 meV steps, 4 fps #6
p_{main} = 1.7 e-4 mbar

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Mar - 22 - 0022 KE = 305 - 320 eV, PE = 100 eV 850 eV

0.1 s calib 100 mV steps, 6-fps #2

Mar - 22 - 0023 KE = ~~200 - 250 eV~~, PE = 100 850 eV

Survey 5 - 850 eV
200 mV steps, 6-fps #1

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